

EVALUATION OF DIGITAL READINESS INDEX (DRI) IN TOURISM SECTOR AS A STEP TOWARD DIGITALIZATION

Camelia Ioana UCENIC ¹
Assoc. Prof., PhD¹
Technical University of Cluj-Napoca
Cluj-Napoca, Memorandumului Str., No. 28, Romania
camelia.ucenic@mis.utcluj.ro ¹
<http://www.utcluj.ro/>

Abstract

Purpose – *The implementation of digital technologies in tourism sector helps the organizations to obtain competitive advantages. An increased availability and accessibility in the market, a greater visibility and a better usage of human force are among benefits of the companies which deal with digital instruments. This study aims to afford a scientific approach in evaluating the level of digitalization for small and medium enterprises from tourism sector using digital readiness index.*

Methodology/approach – *The digital readiness index was evaluated for small and medium hotels located in Chania. They have a minor to average level of digitalization. There are registered 126 hotels in Chania. The reference dimension was utilized as a non-statistical procedure in order to establish the number of respondents. There were selected twenty hotels but were considered only the most important from the center and beach area. The number was enough because they come from a homogenous segment and is sufficient to determine 90-95% of all viable requirements. Digital readiness assessment was done as a multi question valuation of the present situation of digital readiness along two dimensions: technology usage and capacity of the organization. The free toolbox provided by Tourbit was used.*

Findings – *The results show the need of a higher investment in informatics and digitalization, creation of a digital workspace, using of cloud computing and the implementation of IoT.*

Research limitations/implications – *The limitation of this study is given by the number of hotels included in the assessment. A greater number will provide better results.*

Practical implications – *The results allow one to obtain recommendations for raising digital readiness. The SMEs can benefit from consultancy and dedicated trainings.*

Originality/value – *The study is a starting point for companies from tourism sector which intend to raise their level of digitalization. The policy makers can use it in order to design strategies. The study can be extended to other players from tourism.*

Key words: *digitalization, digital readiness index, tourism.*

Introduction

The tourism sector counted as 7% in global trade before pandemic (UNWTO, 2020). Covid-19 had a strong negative impact on it. Travel restrictions forced all players in the sector to think of new solutions. The need for safe holidays and contactless services increased the demand for digital transformations. The use of the internet plays an important role. Virtual tourism was an alternative to traditional tourism despite the fact was not like a real visit. (Akhtar, et all, 2021) Travelers' behaviour and the purchasing habits were changed. They wanted to benefit from new technologies. Tourism organizations as well as travelers needed to improve their digital skills. Much effort was made to increase digital expertise at organization level. Digitalization

provides a higher level of added value. It is considered that the capability of digitalization is not entirely investigated and exploited (Munar and Doering, 2022).

The intensity of digitalization of tourism commodities is different from country to country and from organization to organization. The most common digital tools are digital content, social media, travel blogging, digital storytelling, augmented reality, virtual reality, blockchain. All the players from the tourism sector have to invest in digitalization in order to be agile and obtain a higher degree of customer retention. Digitalization is a must for smart tourism development. Innovation and design of new digital solutions increase the level of competitiveness.

Digitalization in tourism

Digitalization has a great impact in transforming tourism. Nowadays the traditional way of tourism is changed because of digitalization. It supports the destinations and helps to increase sustainability and minimize the negative impact of mass tourism. The pandemic accelerated the demand for digital businesses. Customer requirement for digital services in tourism continuously increased. More than 90% of travelers research online their vacations. (Dredge, 2018). Design of digital solution raises tourism competitiveness. Digital transformation is customer oriented. (Popsa, 2023)

Digital technologies afford knowledge about destinations previously go to see that place. Conventional marketing methods and instruments are transformed by incorporating digital tools. Cost decrease is a positive effect of digitalization. Websites are common digital tools and are considered credible. Social media became a communication channel for different generations of travelers. It is more important for younger generations and decreases with age (Hysa et al, 2021). Social media allows us to establish virtual groups and to impact decision making by revealing travel experiences (Perakakis et al, 2016). Another new element is the implementation of chatbots. Chatbots were established to induce humanlike communication. (Leung and Wen,2020) They are a kind of e-agents which helps customers and provide information in real time. (Tussyadiah, 2020) Blockchain offers secure operations, transparency and traceable payments. (Vidal, 2020). Augmented reality (AR) enhances tourists' experience. It seems to be a direct relation between the visitors' disposition to pay and implementation of AR. Additional revenue is generated by using AR (Chung et al, 2015).

A key factor for getting digitalization is the readiness of stakeholders. Different ways of assessing it are presented in the literature review. The digital readiness index (DRI) is one of them.

Methodology

The digital readiness index (DRI) was evaluated for small and medium hotels with low to average degree of digitalization. The free toolbox provided by Tourbit was used. The calculus of digital readiness index is based on the methodology of multi- attribute decision making. The estimation of the situation is done with the characteristics of the company. Multi- attribute approach is appropriate in solving real life decisions because it is transparent and allows the evaluation and analysis of the company. (Ilijas, 2015)

The digital readiness index (DRI) was assessed for five hotels located in Chania, Greece. This place was selected because it is a very famous one and with over tourism. The tourism sector as well as the population try to find better solutions to assure the sustainable development of the area. The number of arrivals on the airport doubled in the interval 2013-2019. The pandemic affected tourism but less than in other regions. The year 2023 registered the same number of tourists as before Covid. It is expected a higher number of tourists in 2024.

Implementation of innovations and digital technologies can be solutions for overcoming the negative effects of mass tourism.

The reference dimension was utilized as a non-statistical procedure in order to establish the number of respondents. There were selected twenty hotels out of 126 registered in the town but were considered only the most important from the center and beach area. The number was enough because they come from a homogenous segment and is sufficient to determine 90-95% of all viable requirements.

Digital readiness assessment (DRI) was done as a multi question valuation of the present situation along two dimensions: technology usage and capacity of the organization. Technology usage considers three elements: the internal operation and management, customer management and product or service enhancement. The capacity of the organization is analyzed from the point of view of informatics policy, organizational culture and general strategy. Results are graphically represented in two axes. The x axe illustrates technology usage, and the y axe shows the capacity of the organization. Each axe has four levels. The levels of technology usage are beginner, intermediate, proficient and expert. The levels of capacity of organizations are not ready yet, promising, in the process and front-runner.

There are four dials in the graph. The state of the organization is analyzed according with the situation in previous year and the expected situation for this year. The state of the year is illustrated with a circle. An arrow near the circle presents the advancement movements in the close future. This development trend is constructed on the company's expectations. The color of the circle provides a visual illustration of the situation. A red circle shows a company which is a beginner in digitalization. An orange circle is used for a company which is in the developing stage of digitalization. An advanced performance in digitalization is illustrated with a yellow circle. A high level of digitalization is represented with a green circle.

Analysis of technology usage

Technology usage is evaluated by mixing the results concerning the existence of digital tools and their implementation in internal operation and management, product or service development and customer management.

1. Internal operation and management

The company uses software solutions for inside management. The software solutions are not integrated, and they are implemented only for some specific topics. The hotel intends to introduce and integrate additional complete solutions which must be integrated for all inside management. It is recommended to gain more knowledge in the implementation of software solutions. Modern software solutions facilitate more efficient business. The optimization of the business can be done by computer data processing, reliable up-to-date data and an improved communication in the firm.

Digital technologies are used only for communication and collaboration by email and social networks to enable digital connectivity and remote collaboration. It is recommended to create a digital workspace which offers the base of a modern company in a digital environment. The workspace becomes independent by the work location of employees. The remove of communication barriers determines a higher productivity and innovation level.

Cloud computing is used in a very low degree. Cloud computing offers three groups of services: infrastructure, platform and software as a service. The software as a service is an online tool for customers by a booking portal. There is also a very limited extent for a project with the suppliers. It is suggested to be used gradually in some specific areas. Other dedicated web applications for tourism can be implemented.

The hotel feels that blockchain is not important for its activity. A better understanding of it will permit the implementation and to earn benefits. Blockchain can help for more secure, traceable and transparent operations. Business rating or a reward system for loyal customers can be done by using blockchain.

2. Product and service development

The answers provided demonstrate that the hotel does not use digital technologies for value proposition. It is strongly recommended to use them in order to increase the value added for the products and services. Customer relationship management tools can be implemented.

Communication with business partners and suppliers is done mainly through email or by phone. This approach can generate miscommunication and a slow reaction to unexpected fluctuations. Higher level of digitalization of cooperation gives a higher competence.

The hotel did not achieve measurable effects in terms of revenue and costs due digitalization. The identification of areas where can be decreased the cost by implementing digitalization is a first step. A second step can be to set up a dedicated budget for digitalization.

The usage of augmented reality AR and virtual reality VR is not considered important. AR applications can simulate some places from the area and VR can show difficult or inaccessible places of great interest.

3. Customer management

Social media is used as an extra to marketing activities but can be a strategic communication channel. Employees must be educated to use social media as a platform for brand building. To hire a person dedicated only to social media communication is in discussion.

Technologies for relations with customers are not used. They have to be implemented in order to monitor and collect data on customers and sales.

Mobile business is not used. Their practice will permit the customers to access booking information, visits or other trips.

The website is the only digital web channel. Digital web sales channels can be employed. They reduce the sales costs but and increase efficiency. Overreliance in indirect sales channels is an important issue.

Analysis of capacity of the organization

1. Informatics policy

Informatics policy considers digitalization strategy, data management and share of investment. The hotel does not have a digital strategy but is aware of its necessity. The connection with support institutions can help in the design of a proper strategy. Data management includes collection, storage, organization, storage and protection of data. The company has arranged data which can be used for daily activities but is suggested to begin to do it in an integrated way in order to reach the business intelligence. The hotel has already invested in informatics and in information structure but is advised to assign a higher share for these investments. Nowadays the share of investment is less than 1%.

2. Organizational culture

The company does not have a person who takes care exclusively of digitalization and IT. It is recommended to hire one and in medium time create a small IT department. The manager

considers the workers correctly proceed their tasks but without individual commitment. Their dedication can be stimulated by some special financial and nonfinancial rewards. They are ready to work with the new technology and agree to do it. It is necessary to involve the personnel in process of change and digitalization. Nowadays the employees are somewhat autonomous, but the general manager has to increase their opportunity to work independently. Open communication is encouraged between different departments. The employees' cooperation is supported. The innovation of individuals is encouraged but the errors are not accepted. It is suggested the acceptance of mistakes.

3. General strategy

The employees are sent on trainings only in the mandatory framework imposed by legislation. Continuous professional development is a key advantage. It is advised to recognize the key personnel. A management strategy for them must be created. The workforce has the basic knowledge and skills in the digital instruments, but the acquisition of advance skills is mandatory. The company is agile because it can easily adapt at internal and external changes and continuously follows the market trends. The head of the company is responsible for the management. The inclusion of the head of departments is desirable because of their specific knowledge. The decision making is based on the knowledge and data from business reports. Time to time, the opportunities are exploited depending on the estimated level of risk.

Discussion and conclusions

The digitalization readiness index (DRI) analysis was done in terms of technology usage and capacity of the organization. The situation of the hotel was analyzed for the year 2023 and was expected for 2024. Due to confidentiality reasons the company name will be "A". The diagram shows the digital readiness of the company based on two areas. The position and the colour of the circle illustrate the state of the organization. The graph was generated with the Turbit free toolbox.

As can be observed for the year 2023, the company is a beginner from the point of view of technology usage and is promising from the point of view the capacity of the organization. The circle is red in the graph and is located in the left down dial. An arrow goes from this circle to the left-up dial. The circle associated with the year 2024 is orange and shows an intermediate level of technology usage. An improvement is noticed also in the capacity of the organization. It is in the transition from a promising situation to an in the process situation.

The implementation of the above proposed recommendation will help the hotel to increase the digitalization readiness index. The personnel must be trained in different areas of expertise in digitalization, key personnel have to receive better knowledge and skills. A special person must be nominated for social media and in medium run an IT department must be created. A higher percentage of revenue must be invested in informatics and digitalization. Implementation of innovative technologies at product/ service level as well as at managerial level will help the company to gain competitive advantage and to increase the market share.

Figure 1: Digitalization readiness index for company A

Most of the selected organizations were positioned as beginners or intermediate from a technology usage point of view last year. Just one company was proficient. The situation was better in accordance with the capacity of the organization, more organizations being in the left upper dial.

The results indicate a great need of investment in the digitalization, creation of a digital workspace and using cloud computing in specific areas. Last but not least, the internet of things IoT is known and implemented to a low degree. It can offer the tourists the capacity to control accommodation parameters. More organizations must be included in the study. They can be grouped according to the needs and special programs can be tailored.

References

Akhtar, N., et al

2021

Post-COVID 19 Tourism: Will Digital Tourism Replace Mass Tourism?. *Sustainability*, 13(10), pp. 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13105352>

Chung, N. et al

2015

"Tourists' intention to visit a destination: The role of augmented reality (AR) application for a heritage site", *Computers in Human Behaviour*

Dredge, D., et al

2018

Digitalisation in Tourism: In-dept analysis of challenges and opportunities. Low Value procedure FRO-SME-17-C-091-A for Executive Agency for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (EASME) Virtual Tourism Observatory. Aalborg University, Copenhagen.

Hysa, B. et al

2021

"Social Media Usage by Different Generations as a Tool for Sustainable Tourism Marketing in Society 5.0 Idea" *Sustainability* 13, no. 3: 1018. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13031018>

Ilijaz, T. and Borsnar, M.

2015

"Assessment of cloud high performance computing potential for SMEs, The 13th International Symposium on Operations research, Slovenia

Leung, X. Y. and Wen, H.

2020

"Chatbot usage in restaurant takeout orders: A comparison study of three ordering methods", *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 45, 377-386.

Munar, A.M.; Doering, A.,

2022

COVID-19 the intruder: A philosophical journey with Jean-Luc Nancy into pandemic strangeness and tourism. *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 43, pp.1-10
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tmp.2022.100999>

Perakakis, E., et all

2016

"Social media as a marketing tool for Greek destinations", *Tourismos: An International Multidisciplinary Journal of Tourism*, 11, 157-181.

Popsa, R.

2023

"Digitalization, a strategic approach for the travel and tourism industry", *Expert Journal of marketing*, 11(2), pp 181-197, ISSN: 2344-6773

UNWTO

2020

AIUla Framework for Inclusive Community Development through Tourism. Available online: <https://www.e-unwto.org/doi/book/10.18111/9789284422159>

Vidal, B.

2020

What we can expect from blockchain technology in tourism, *Digital Customer Experience*